

	Document:	D8.1. Communication and Dissemination plan (CDP)		
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Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP)

WP8 – Deliverable 8.1

CIRC-PACK - Towards circular economy in the
plastic packaging value chain

Grant agreement: 730423

Prepared by: ICLEI EURO

Date: 30/10/2017

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 730423.

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DELIVERABLE FACTSHEET

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Dissemination level	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU = Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the EC)
<input type="checkbox"/>	RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC)
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Diffusion list

Approvals

Author/s	ICLEI EURO
Task Leader	ICLEI EURO
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ABBREVIATIONS

CA: Consortium Agreement
 CDP: Communication and Dissemination Plan
 EC: European Commission
 SME: Small and Medium Enterprise
 WP: Work Package
 T.X.X: Task
 D.X.X: Deliverable

PARTNERS SHORT NAMES

CIRCE: FUNDACION CIRCE – RESEARCH CENTRE FOR ENERGY RESOURCES AND CONSUMPTION
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MBP: MATER-BIOPOLYMER SRL
BUMAGA BV: BUMAGA BV
TECNOPACKAGING: NUEVAS TECNOLOGIAS PARA EL DESARROLLO DE PACKAGING Y PRODUCTOS AGROALIMENTARIOS CON COMPONENTE PLASTICA SL
MI-PLAST: MI-PLAST DOO ZA PROIZVODNJU TRGOVINU I PRUZANJE USLUGA - MI-PLAST LLC MANUFACTURING, TRADING AND SERVICES MIPLAST
GRUPO SADA: GRUPO SADA P A SA
SAPONIA D.D.: SAPONIA KEMIJSKA, PREHRAMBENA I FARMACEUTSKA INDUSTRIJA D.D.
FATER: Fater S.p.A.
CRF: CENTRO RICERCHE FIAT SCPA
UNE: ASOCIACION ESPANOLA DE NORMALIZACION
RINA-C: RINA CONSULTING
EKODENGE: EKODENGE MUHENDISLIK MIMARLIK DANISMANLIK TICARET ANONIM SIRKETI
ECOEMBES: ECOEMBALAJES ESPANA, S.A.
CITY OF RIJEKA: GRAD RIJEKA-GRADSKO VIJECE
KARTALMUN: KARTAL BELEDIYE BASKANLIGI
CALAF IND: CALAF TECHNIQUES INDUSTRIALS SL
OCU EDICIONES: OCU EDICIONES SA
ICLEI EURO: ICLEI EUROPEAN SECRETARIAT GMBH (ICLEI EUROPASEKRETARIAT GMBH)
PLASTIPOLIS: PLASTIPOLIS

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The Communication and Dissemination Plan explains how the project will communicate its developments and outcomes, and how the consortium will ensure visibility of the project and dissemination of its results throughout its duration.

It provides a context analysis on EU commitment, an action plan and targets to attain a circular economy, as well as general and specific objectives for WP8. It identifies key stakeholder groups and establishes relevant messages for each target audience. It defines the branding and promotion tools, and the channels to be used, describing the methodology to be followed for carrying out and tracking each activity and their related timing while assigning roles and responsibilities.

The aim is to put in place all necessary measures to achieve the desired outcomes, guiding partners in the implementation of WP8 through a coherent, structured and effective approach, and to constantly monitor activities to easily adapt their implementation if necessary.

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1 STRATEGY

1.1 Project context and communication objectives

In December 2014, the European Commission withdrew its legislative proposal on waste, committing to use its horizontal working methods to present a new package which would cover the full economic cycle - from responsible sourcing of primary raw materials to production and consumption, including waste management and market development for secondary raw materials¹.

As many natural resources are finite and their price has increased at twice the rate of wage growth over the past decade², it is essential to find an environmentally and economically sustainable way of using them. This implies a switch from a linear 'take-make-dispose' model towards a **circular economy** approach - where materials are highly valued and maintain their value for as long as possible, and waste and resource use are minimised through reuse, repairs, refurbishment and recycling good practices³, providing consumers with innovative and more durable products that provide monetary savings and an increased quality of life⁴. Circular economy is more than just old-fashioned recycling: it is the creation of a new business model in which products are designed to be stripped down to their smallest components after they've been used, with these parts then re-inserted back into the production chain instead of being discarded⁵.

The EU **Circular Economy Package** adopted in 2015 aims to stimulate Europe's transition towards a circular economy through measures that will cut resource use, reduce waste and greenhouse gas emissions, boost recycling, and eventually foster energy savings, enhancing global competitiveness as well as sustainable economic growth and generating new jobs, in line with EU strategic objectives. The Package consists of an [EU Action Plan for the Circular Economy](#) and an [annex to the action plan](#) which sets out the timeline for when the actions will be completed⁶.

The revised legislative proposals on waste⁷ set clear targets for the reduction of waste and establish an ambitious and credible long-term path for waste management and recycling. Key elements of the revised waste proposal include:

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/environment/circular-economy/index_en.htm

² <https://euobserver.com/economic/127944>

³ <http://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/infographics/circulareconomy/public/index.html>

⁴ http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_MEMO-15-6204_en.htm

⁵ <https://euobserver.com/economic/127944>

⁶ http://ec.europa.eu/environment/circular-economy/index_en.htm

⁷ Further relevant information here: [Proposed Directive on Waste](#) , [Proposed Directive on Packaging Waste](#) , [Proposed Directive on Landfill](#)

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- A common EU target for recycling 65% of municipal waste and 75% of packaging waste by 2030;
- A binding landfill target to reduce landfills to a maximum of 10% of municipal waste by 2030;
- A ban on the disposal of separately-collected waste into landfills;
- Promotion of economic instruments to discourage the proliferation of landfills;
- Simplified and improved definitions and harmonised calculation methods for recycling rates throughout the EU;
- Concrete measures to promote the re-use of waste and stimulate industrial symbiosis - turning one industry's by-products into another industry's raw materials;
- Economic incentives for producers to put greener products on the market and support recovery and recycling schemes (e.g. for packaging, batteries, electric and electronic equipment, vehicles)⁸.

This transition is financially supported by the European Structural and Investment Fund (ESIF) with €5.5 billion allocated to waste management, the EU funding programme for research and innovation Horizon 2020 with €650 million, as well as investments at the national level⁹.

Innovation and change will bring benefits but also create challenges. For instance, scientists, businesses and governments are only beginning to understand how to recycle complex plastics, avoiding the waste of valuable and increasingly rare materials, while keeping potentially hazardous substances out of the biosphere where they could affect ecosystems and also human health¹⁰.

In this framework and to contribute to the above-mentioned targets, CIRC-PACK sets the ambitious objectives of creating, testing and validating alternative bio-based and recyclable plastics for multiple purposes, as well as new types of multilayer and multi-material packaging that can be easily separated, which is expected to increase recovery rates and quality while reducing the amount of waste sent landfills. This will be done through a systemic approach and large scale demonstrations that encompass value and supply chains in their entirety and engage all actors involved¹¹, as well as proposing new business models and regulation best practices. The project will run over a period of three years.

Awareness, communication and dissemination actions targeting specific audiences with tailored messages are key to the success of this project. Based on a preparatory resource mapping exercise in which all CIRC-PACK partners took part, this strategy describes the communication objectives, target groups, key messages, approach, channels and products, as well as the validation, monitoring, tracking and evaluation, and reporting procedures which will be put in place. Tasks within WP8 will run from month 1 until beyond the end of the project under the leadership and coordination of ICLEI EURO and the support and monitoring of Plastipolis, who will be responsible for T.8.3 - Dissemination and communication actions, while CIRCE will also support and consultation as project coordinator.

⁸ http://ec.europa.eu/environment/circular-economy/index_en.htm

⁹ http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_IP-15-6203_en.htm

¹⁰ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/circular-economy-in-europe>

¹¹ <http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/opportunities/h2020/topics/circ-01-2016-2017.html>

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This strategy and plan will undergo a minimum of two updates - in month 12 and in month 24 - to respond to any changing needs of an evolving project.

WP8 actions will be conceived and implemented with the purpose of meeting the following **general communication objective**:

Widely spread CIRC-PACK results among the main target audiences identified in WP2 and WP7, raising awareness about the project's technical, environmental, social and economic benefits.

In order to achieve this main objective, WP8 will pursue several **specific objectives**:

1. Define an agile communication strategy adapted to the different target groups and messages
 - To plan to achieve the desired outcomes;
 - To guide partners throughout communication and dissemination activities through a meaningful, coherent, structured and effective approach.

2. Prepare a corporate image pack and a set of materials for the promotion and the comprehensive dissemination of the project and its outcomes
 - To build a recognisable brand of CIRC-PACK solutions with visibility and reputation;
 - To raise awareness on, interest in, and understanding of the topics of circular economy, plastic packaging waste and the related environmental impact, as well as on resource efficiency and waste management, and to generate market demand for the developed solutions;
 - To provide a regular flow of information to target audiences;
 - To bring end-users closer to the product design and production phases, engaging them into participatory co-design processes, addressing their needs and boosting new consumption patterns that reduce over-production and waste;
 - To show citizens and tax payers the added value of European cooperation in addressing common problems relevant to their everyday lives and enhance the feeling of citizenship
 - To showcase achievements and successes in international and national media as well as in scientific and specialised publications;
 - To keep all partners actively involved in the project and support all stakeholders - mainly entrepreneurs, industries and researchers – in order to exploit and make best use of results;
 - To foster target groups' commitment and create an enabling legislative and regulatory environment which facilitates market uptake and replication of the developed innovative solutions and business models, and promotes public-private partnership opportunities;
 - To draw the attention of potential partners and investors who may want to provide additional resources for further developing the project.

3. Execute and monitor the Communication and Dissemination Plan with continuous engagement with the main target groups and tailored messages while measuring, controlling, managing and quickly adapting the strategy, if needed.

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1.2 Key stakeholders and messages

Overarching messages:

Resources are limited and increasingly expensive. We need to be smart and sustainable about their use, adopting a new sustainable model based on reuse-repair-recycle approach.

Our production and consumption patterns affect resource stocks and generate waste, which too often ends up in landfills, where plastics will remain virtually forever. Reinventing plastics for the circular economy and addressing their lifecycle is the solution to this problem.

CIRC-PACK sees plastic waste as a valuable resource that should re-enter the value chain.

CIRC-PACK will develop and validate bio-based, compostable and recyclable plastics, plus eco-friendly multilayer / multi-material packaging, and enhance recycling technologies.

CIRC-PACK believes that recycling rates in Europe and the quality of recovered materials can be improved to gain secondary raw materials for different purposes.

Creating an enabling business and regulatory environment is crucial to market uptake of the proposed innovations for resource efficiency and waste management.

Stakeholders at all levels and from all sectors are encouraged to contribute to the success of the project. CIRC-PACK solutions will be available to all and will benefit a broad audience.

Table 1. Key benefits brought by the project

CIRC-PACK is expected to bring multiple benefits	
TECHNOLOGICAL	ECONOMIC
Bridge research-innovation gap validating technologies for manufacture industry	Cost reduction for materials, performance, EU plastic industry competitiveness
Better equipment and process performance	Savings from implementation of EU legislation (landfill targets)
Feasible customized solutions and materials for different sectors and needs	Reduction of dependence on fossil fuels variable cost
ENVIRONMENTAL	SOCIAL
Decrease in extraction / transport of raw materials	Health, safety, well-being and quality of life
Reduction of environmental impact of land filling	Long-lasting innovative products for consumers
Reduction of energy dependence on fossil fuels	Job creation
Resource efficiency and sustainability	Risk reduction in investment and decision making

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As the plastics economy is highly fragmented and uncoordinated, the lack of collaboration between stakeholders and the proliferation of technologies and standards in the sector are among the main factors hindering the uptake of promising innovative solutions. Therefore, ensuring regular exchange information and stimulating networking are crucial points to achieve the above-mentioned objectives.

The identified target groups are based on a preliminary survey of CIRC-PACK stakeholders done in the proposal, as well as on the definition of the stakeholders involved in the plastic packaging value chain carried out in WP2. Deliverables 7.1 and 7.2 - Preliminary and final market analysis (due in months 12 and 30) and Deliverable 7.5 - Business plan will be used to redefine these target groups, if needed.

Table 2.1. Primary target groups of the CIRC-PACK Project

Primary target groups	
Target groups	Tailored messages
<p>PUBLIC AUTHORITIES AND REGULATORS</p> <p>European, regional and local public authorities, policy and decision makers, practitioners, waste managers</p> <p>Regulators and standards organisations in the environmental, food, automobile, hygiene and cosmetics, waste, plastic and disposable / packaging sectors</p> <p>Public procurement networks</p> <p><i>All the groups above can contribute to market uptake. The focus will be on CIRC-PACK regions and other municipalities with waste management problems.</i></p>	<p>Need to support the market uptake and replication of CIRC-PACK solutions* with relevant and adequate legislation, strategies, standards, measures, financing schemes, and informational/awareness raising campaigns. In particular, the regulation best practices proposed by CIRC-PACK can support in this process.</p> <p>Creating opportunities to facilitate stakeholder engagement at all levels and across sectors, and also adopting CIRC-PACK solutions* for public procurement, will help solve major waste management issues, reduce related costs for public administrations (including health costs), stimulate the economy and result in a sustainable and safer choice for citizens.</p>
<p>VALUE CHAIN ACTORS - PRIVATE SECTOR</p> <p>Plastic suppliers, material converters, brand owners (retailers), distributors, clusters and associations of companies working in the packaging sector as well as in other industries.</p> <p>These actors may want to use bio-based, recyclable, and/or recycled materials and eco-designs for their products as well as enhanced technologies, methods, and business models, and may become our partners and spread the word on these solutions.*</p>	<p>CIRC-PACK will demonstrate eco-friendly and customisable bio-based, compostable and recycled plastics which the manufacturing industry can use to reduce costs of sourcing raw materials. In addition, the project will demonstrate the availability of better technological equipment and processes to improve performance and become more effective and competitive on the market as well as develop new sustainable business models.</p>
<p>THE SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY</p>	<p>Possibility to contribute to CIRC-PACK innovative and sustainable solutions*, disseminate them, exchange</p>

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<p>Universities and other research and education organisations, research centres, international and national technology clusters and networks as knowledge generators and innovative waste solutions providers who may contribute to our work and have an interest in research findings.</p> <p>Special attention will be paid to those in the fields of chemistry, design, material science, engineering, environment, management and policy.</p>	<p>with experts and practitioners, and use them as a knowledge base to build new knowledge.</p>
<p>WASTE / RECYCLING SECTOR COMPANIES</p> <p>Waste recovery actors and waste technology providers, including for organic and paper waste, interested in partnerships or in project findings.</p>	<p>Availability of free (EU-funded) enhanced methods and technologies for sorting, recycling and monitoring to get reliable quality recycled plastics. These recovered plastics represent a valuable resource as they can be sold back to manufacturers as source materials (secondary raw materials) adapted to different sectors and needs. These come with new business models to ensure that the investment in these innovations is sustainable.</p>

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Table 2.2. Secondary target groups of the CIRC-PACK Project

Secondary target groups	
Target groups	Tailored messages
<p>CONSUMERS</p> <p>With particular reference to women’s groups, as women’s choices play a key role in household economics.</p> <p>These are the end-users directly affected by the outcomes of the project, and are those consuming resources and generating waste. Consumers may be citizens but also businesses and public administrations.</p>	<p>The EU is investing taxpayers’ money to make it possible to get innovative, safer, cheaper, long-lasting, eco-friendly, separable plastic packaging and products for multiple uses (cars, hygiene, etc.).</p> <p>Citizens’ acceptance and feedback is key in this process, as well as a shift in their consumer behaviour. This emerging sector is also expected to create new job opportunities and competitiveness across Europe.</p>
<p>POTENTIAL INVESTORS</p> <p>Banks, entrepreneurs, foundations, funds and others who may provide additional resources in the future, either to this specific research or to projects in the same field.</p>	<p>Investing in expanding and implementing innovative and sustainable solutions* for attaining a circular economy creates immediate return on investment and a positive image in the eyes’ of society, bringing benefits to many sectors. In particular, the new business models developed guarantee the sustainability of the investment.</p>

Table 2.3. Multipliers of the CIRC-PACK Project communication and dissemination activities

Multipliers	
Multiplier	How to tailor messages
<p>MEDIA</p> <p>International and national outlets and websites, both general and specialised</p>	<p>Communication to the media will focus on the overarching messages, on disseminating specific project results and events, and on highlighting CIRC-PACK benefits. Depending on the type and the scope of the outlet, they can report on exciting results as well as boost advocacy and dissemination for improved awareness and understanding, acceptance, commitment and action related to bio-based, recyclable and recycled plastics.</p>
<p>THE CIVIL SOCIETY + OTHER INFLUENCERS</p> <p>Environmental and health NGOs, citizen and consumer associations, etc.</p>	<p>Communication to this target group will mainly focus on how CIRC-PACK solutions* address existing problems (in their respective field of interest), as well as on the additional benefits they bring to society.</p>

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Politicians, entrepreneurs, activists, celebrities, bloggers and social media stars.	
STAKEHOLDERS' NETWORKS The action of a group of stakeholders can help raising awareness among other related groups. Special attention is to be paid to stakeholders involved in other EU projects - especially from the same call - for the creation of practical synergies.	The messages in this case depends on the type of stakeholders, stressing the fact that helping to disseminate project results is essential to the success of the project.

*"Solutions" refers to **CIRC-PACK solutions**: new bio-based, compostable, recyclable materials and eco-designs for packaging and plastic products, as well as enhanced sorting and recycling technologies, new business models and regulation best practices.

Project partners' employees are as well a relevant stakeholder group to address, because the whole workforce rarely is aware and informed about the development of innovative actions being carried out in their own organisations.

Effective internal communication regarding ongoing projects and tasks can potentially contribute to creative ideas to improve the process, mitigate risks and correct deviations.

1.3 Visual and written identity

During the first months of the project, CIRCE and ICLEI developed the following branding tools, also based on the ideas and suggestions received from partners at the Kick-off Meeting:

1. An easy recognisable logo and an anagram - with different colour variations - in print and web format;

2. A corporate style guide for project partners on the correct use of the project identity as well as the EU logo, the legal content and the disclaimer acknowledging the funding received by the EU and limiting EU responsibility for content (this represents an obligation therefore the information has also been made available in Annex I), the colour palette and the fonts;

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3. A PowerPoint template for presentations;
4. Four Word templates to be used for agendas, minutes, deliverables and to track participants' attendance at meetings;
5. A written identity document with a claim.

In addition, a professional designer created:

6. A header and a footer to be used to develop corporate communication and dissemination materials such as leaflets and posters,
7. A design for the project website.

The documents mentioned in the points above have been uploaded onto the project Intranet EMDESK and shared with all project participants. By using these templates, the consortium will ensure that the branding is consistent throughout the project. All partners' logos as well as the project's website URL, social media accounts and e-mail address appear on those templates to be used for external communication and dissemination purposes.

A selection of keywords and concepts which best define the project was identified by partners during a brainstorming exercise, which is to be highlighted in all communication activities:

Circularity / Circular economy / Plastic(s) / Bio-(based) materials / Packaging / Bio-degradability / Product sustainability / Environmental protection / Environmental impact reduction / Ecology / Solutions / Innovation / Renewable resources / Rethink / Lifecycle / Waste management / Waste reduction / Waste recovery / Sorting / Recyclability / Compostability / Monitoring / Green polymers / Resource efficiency / Eco-design / Multilayer / Multi-material / Multi-sectorial / Value chain actors / Large-scale demonstrations / bioplastics

1.4 Products and channels

A range of channels and products will be used to reach out to and engage with the different target groups on the development, lessons learnt and results of the project, with a focus on stimulating interaction and exchange. The related methods, activities and tools are described in detail below.

Project website and newsletter

A Typo3-based project website will be developed by ICLEI and go live within the first year of the project. It will be the main public window and interface of CIRC-PACK with stakeholders, showcasing all public information about the project and its developments, the main topics, the consortium, deliverables and events.

The website look and feel - developed by a professional web design agency - will be based on the CIRC-PACK visual identity guidelines. An example is provided below:

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Figure 1. Web design developed for CIRC-PACK website

The URL will be www.circpack.eu and the website will have the following structure (some keywords may change based on a better assessment of project needs):

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Figure 2. Structure developed for CIRC-PACK website

It will be intuitive, user-friendly and fully responsive in order to be accessible from desktop computers, laptops, netbooks, notepads and smartphones. ICLEI will ensure it is constantly updated, technically operative, and meets usability criteria. Regular posting of original content will include news (not only strictly related to the project, but also to the topics in general) and upcoming events. A consistent use of keywords and headings as well as linking with other related websites will be essential to quickly attaining a high ranking in Google and other search engines.

A QR code printed on the project communication and dissemination products (leaflet, poster, business cards, etc.) will help bring visitors to the website.

The project newsletter will be sent out quarterly to those stakeholders who will subscribe using a form on the website. Their contact details will not be shared with third parties. The newsletter will be edited by ICLEI with contributions coming from all partners, with approval from CIRCE. It will be an HTML email that is visually in line with the CIRC-PACK project identity, and it will be distributed with either the Vertical Response or Mailchimp email software.

Social media

A Twitter account and a LinkedIn group on *circular economy* have been created for the project, and they will be shared with PlastiCircle - a project from the same Horizon 2020 call which focuses on improving plastic

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packaging recycling, in which several CIRC-PACK beneficiaries are also involved, in order to increase the impact and reach out a wider audience. These accounts will show the logos of both the projects. These will be managed by ICLEI with the contribution of all partners.

An average of 4 tweets per week will be posted, based on the needs of the project, in order to:

- Raise interest in the topics and in the project, especially with facts and figures;
- Attract visitors to the project website;
- Disseminate videos;
- Share news on advancements in the field (also not directly related to the project);
- Target influencers and build relationships;
- Announce events and workshops.

The Twitter account chosen is *@circ_economy* .

Hashtags to be used are:

#circpack #h2020
(fixed)

#circulareconomy #waste #plastic #packaging #plasticpackaging #recycle
(these are optional and can be translated into national languages)

All partners are encouraged to retweet, quote or translate the tweets into their language, and to participate in EU events also via Twitter, interacting through the use of event hashtags. ICLEI will seek to engage with project partners' existing social media channels to boost the presence of the *@circ_economy* account.

The LinkedIn group *Circular economy. Plastic packaging from waste to resource* ([linkedin.com/groups/12055948](https://www.linkedin.com/groups/12055948)) will address more a professional audience e.g., actors along the value chain, such as waste managers and technology providers, researchers. It will be used for:

- Sharing updates and conference presentations;
- Discussing project outcomes, getting feedback from beneficiaries and networking with stakeholders working at similar projects;
- Disseminating publications and workshop invitations;
- Posting opportunities related to the project.

LinkedIn is also a relevant channel, as Twitter does not have the same level of popularity in every country or with every target group. Consortium partners from CIRC-PACK and PlastiCircle will be encouraged to maintain the group alive by posting one blog per month in turn, documenting project progress.

All partners with an interest in public procurement from the demand side (public actors, academia, civil society organisations) will be invited to contribute to a private group on *Waste, Resources and the Circular*

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Economy on the Public Procurement Forum managed by ICLEI. A sub-group on plastic packaging may be created for CIRC-PACK and PlastiCircle only, however partners will be able to participate in the discussions going on within the main group, which has already 133 members from previous waste management projects.

Project e-mail

An alias info@circpack.eu has been set up, directing e-mails towards the coordinators' mailboxes, and it will be displayed on all external communication and dissemination materials, including the project website and social media channels.

Leaflets, posters and banner

A first version of leaflets and posters - presenting project aims, demo cases and expected benefits - will be created by ICLEI by month 12, while a new poster and leaflet - displaying final project results - will be ready by month 32. The language will be understandable to a general audience.

Both leaflets and posters will be published on the project website, in low resolution, and uploaded onto the project Intranet, in high resolution, for downloading.

Leaflets will be initially printed by ICLEI to be distributed to all partners in the consortium for use at external events. ICLEI will also send them to key EU officials and targeted stakeholders.

Partners will print posters as needed, which can be used at events organised by the project.

ICLEI will also produce a roll-up banner with the project logo, website URL and a key message(s) to be placed in front of exhibition stands or speakers' table at conferences.

Events

Event organisation will be led by Plastipolis and supported by ICLEI as well as project partners, along the whole duration of the project, and will include:

- A dissemination meeting with the main stakeholders and the European Commission, to present the project, its aims, the benefits expected as well as the first findings (by month 12, in Auvergne Rhône-Alpes region office in Brussels);
- An edition of Breakfast at Sustainability's - a small, informal meeting hosted by the ICLEI Brussels office which will address sustainability, circular economy and waste management issues

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developments and will target high level policy makers as well as regional and local public authorities (tentative date: month 24);

- A series of six workshops or conferences across Europe (two on each Demo case) - these will attract 50 participants each and will take place back-to-back or in the context of larger relevant events to ensure high stakeholder participation and to reach a wider audience (dates will be identified on this base). The objective is to discuss specific research results and receive input from outside the consortium, as well as to trigger new replication projects and to disseminate both the recommendations developed during the project and the preliminary results to the targeted beneficiaries. These workshops will mainly target value chain actors, waste recovery managers and public authorities at the regional and national level. Scientists and journalists will also be invited.

Tentative list of workshops, taking place in the countries of Demo case leaders:

- Decoupling plastics from fossil feedstocks - Italy
- Developing innovative formats and testing materials - Netherlands
- Creating an effective after-use plastics economy - Spain

Other workshops on the same topics may take place in France, Croatia, Turkey or Germany. Otherwise webinars can be hosted on Plastipolis dedicated platform.

- A final conference where results will be announced together with a discussion of lessons learned and opportunities for further extension of the project's results (by month 36).

A list of free facilities and equipment (conference rooms, projectors, etc.) available at partners' premises has been already set up in order to identify suitable locations for meetings and events.

Plastipolis will prepare a concept note prior to organising each workshop. This document will be submitted to the WP8 leader 4 months in advance and will provide an overview of the event date, venue, purpose, target audience, available resources, expected support, promotional channels and products to be considered for the event.

All partners are encouraged to suggest relevant contacts to be invited to attend all these events.

Scientific publications

CIRC-PACK will create a number of technical, publishable results, which will all be available under open access. All partners responsible for producing such results will consult the European Commission's "Guidelines to the Rules on open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020" (http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf). The aim behind this is to allow other researchers and projects to build on research results from CIRC-PACK, encourage collaboration, speed up innovation, and allow for transparency and the involvement of citizens and society.

Any peer-reviewed scientific research articles or research data which the CIRC-PACK consortium deems suitable for publication will be done so via the above mentioned open data guidelines. Project partners are to submit these publications to ICLEI EURO who will ensure that the reports are available for download on the project website. All partners will additionally report their scientific publications in the Participant Portal during Periodic Reports. The template for reporting scientific publications can be found within the periodic reporting template here:

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http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/gm/reporting/h2020-tmpl-periodic-rep_en.pdf

Media and press releases

A first press release in the languages of participating countries has been issued at the beginning of the project, and new ones (at least 4) will be sent out whenever project outcomes, publications or events will become available.

ICLEI is responsible for drafting and disseminating international press releases that can be then translated and adapted by partners to the national and local contexts (e.g. also adding their own press contact and organisation description) and sent out to their own media contacts. When using corporate templates and press software, partners will ensure that the project logo, contacts and website as well as all partners' logos appear on the press release.

Press releases will be published on the project website and all language versions will be shared with the consortium through the project Intranet, so that translated materials can be shared by partners and used in any suitable context.

ICLEI has defined those partners who will be responsible for translations and put together a list of relevant media outlets which will be constantly updated to maximise the press impact. Additionally, any content produced will be distributed via online information multipliers and dedicated platforms such as Cordis Wire and Alpha Galileo.

In addition, ICLEI will regularly be in touch with EU Communications Officers and use EU resources - including Horizon Magazine, Horizon Project Stories, Research EU Results Magazine, Research EU Focus, EU Newsletters, Futuris Magazine, DG RTD Headlines, CORDIS Wire, and the EASME news blog as much as possible to highlight project activities and results.

Eventually, a press kit will be prepared, posted on the website, distributed to the media in a pack at the project events and workshops, and updated as needed or at least after each strategy review.

It will contain:

- The initial press release introducing the project as well as the most recent press release, or the most recent leaflet of the project
- The project PowerPoint presentation
- The written identity of the project
- Frequently Asked Questions (and answers)
- A list of "tweetable" facts about the topic and the project
- An infographic illustrating the benefits brought by CIRC-PACK
- Pictures that can be published by journalists (for which CIRC-PACK owns the copyright or which are copyright free for commercial use and modification).

The involvement of public administrations and local authorities in the project will guarantee a strong influence on local media, which will be invited to the main events and project showcases.

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Project videos

Videos are very direct means of communication and normally achieve a higher impact than a written text. They are particularly suitable to transfer scientific and technical concepts to non-experts and engage stakeholders.

For this reasons, the consortium envisages to develop two videos of about two minutes each in English. These will be created respectively at the beginning and at the end of the project and will present CIRC-PACK, its messages and impacts, including:

- Animated elements, graphics and infographics illustrating key circular economy concepts, summarising demonstration activities as well as plastic waste recovery solutions implemented during CIRC-PACK, and the benefits demonstrated by the project;
- Footage, e.g. interviews or explanations given by a project participant, scenes from plants and laboratories;
- Audio tracks for the narrative.

CIRCE and ICLEI will work together preparing the synopsis, the content, the story board and the audio scripts, while an external video-maker and editor will deal with the implementation.

The videos will be in both high and low definition in order to be shared - by all partners - through the website, YouTube and social media channels, preferably to be combined with press releases and media activities, and used to present the project at events.

Partners may at any time record experience videos and send them to ICLEI, who will archive this footage to be used for future video production, to respond to media requests, and/or to generate some buzz on social media.

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Project partners' channels

The following channels owned by the partners of the consortium have been mapped to be used to further disseminate and amplify the messages:

Table 3. CIRC-PACK project partners' communication channels

Organisation	Website	Twitter	LinkedIn	Other social media	Newsletter	Other channels partner manages
CIRCE	www.fcirce.es	@fcirce	es.linkedin.com/company/circe-research-centre-for-energy-resources-and-consumption	www.facebook.com/fcirce		www.regions4resource.eu
AITIIP	www.aitiip.com	@aitiip	www.linkedin.com/company/aitiip-centro-tecnol-gico	www.facebook.com/aitiip.centrotecnologico		Hyperbiocoat.eu, Recysite.eu, Funguschain.eu, Bioplastictrain.eu and related social networks
NOVAMONT Group (incl. MATER-BIOTECH and MATER-BIOPOLYMER)	www.novamont.com	@Novamont	www.linkedin.com/company/novamont/notifications?goback=&trk=hb_ntf_AGGREGATED_COMPANY	www.facebook.com/novamont www.instagram.com/novamont_group	X	Bit3G, FIRST2RUN, PULPACKTION, FUNGHUSCHAIN, BIOCONCEPT
BUMAGA	www.bumaga.nl	@bumaga_arnhem	www.linkedin.com/company-beta/2052049			Actinpak.eu, BANUS, newgenpak.eu, FUTUREBioPack, ProgRESS
TECNO PACKAGING	www.tecnopackaging.com	@tecnopackaging		es-es.facebook.com/Tecnopackaging		
MI-PLAST	www.mi-plast.eu					FUNGUSCHAIN, PULPACKTION, HYPERBIOCOAT, RES URBIS, REFUCOAT, AFTERLIFE

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Grupo SADA	www.sadagrupo.com	@sadagrupo	es.linkedin.com/company/grupo-sada	es-es.facebook.com/PollosGrupoSada		DIBBIOPACK, GOLDENFOOD, CHAMPILOPAGE
SAPONIA	www.saponia.hr			hr-hr.facebook.com/Saponia		funguschain.eu, EMBRACED
FATER	www.fatergroup.com					EMBRACED
CRF	www.crf.it					
UNE	www.une.org	@NormasUNE	www.linkedin.com/company-beta/11007055/		X	
RINA Consulting (incl. RINA SERVICES)	www.rinaconsulting.org www.rina.org	@RINA1861	www.linkedin.com/company-beta/41262/			rehap.eu, fissacproject.eu, hiserproject.eu
EKODENGE	www.ekodenge.com	@ekodengeas	www.linkedin.com/company/ekodenge	www.facebook.com/ekodengeas, architizer.com/firms/ekodenge-mimarlik, worldarchitecture.org/profiles/hpzn/seda_temizer_yntem-profile-pages.html, preview.mailerlite.com/v1v2e1		nature4cities.eu, fissacproject.eu
ECOEMBES	www.ecoembes.com	@TheCircularLab				thecircularlab.com
RIJEKA	www.rijeka.hr					
KARTAL	www.kartal.bel.tr	@ kartalbid		www.facebook.com/Kartalbid		birnefesyasam.com, kartalgazetesi.net, r2cities.eu, newspapers and magazines
CALAF IND	www.calafindustrial.com, www.calafgrup.com					
OCU	www.ocu.org	@consumidores	www.linkedin.com/company-beta/1097078	www.facebook.com/consumidoresocu, www.youtube.com/user/ocutv	X	OCU Compra Maestra, Salud magazines, Test-Achats , Deco Proteste, Altroconsumo magazines
ICLEI	www.iclei-europe.org	@ICLEI_Europe	www.linkedin.com/company-beta/49060/ (ICLEI Global)	www.flickr.com/photos/iclei_europe, www.youtube.com/user/icleieurope	X	www.urbanwins.eu and related social media,

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						PlastiCircle channels, SP Platform, PPI Platform
PLASTIPOLIS	www.plastipolis.fr	@plastipolis	www.linkedin.com/company/plastipolis			

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Internal communication

ICLEI, as the WP8 leader, will take part in Steering Committee meetings where developments related to the other WPs will be brought to the attention of the partners. The responsible partners for each deliverable must fill in a dissemination potential form attached to the Deliverable template (which will not be submitted) and establish the timing for result disclosure. All partners in the consortium are expected to inform the project coordinator and WP leader on relevant outcomes, publications and events, as well as in the participation in external events well in advance, in order to identify appropriate actions for communication and dissemination.

A mailing list has been set up to facilitate the correspondence between WP8 coordinators and the communication and dissemination correspondents in each partner organisation. Bilateral and multilateral videoconferences will be organised by the WP8 leader with the members of this group based on project needs. All final communication materials will be posted on the website and/or the Intranet and the links shared with partners via e-mail.

Other internal communication issues concerning the whole consortium have been already described in Grant Agreement as well as in Deliverable 1.1 - Project Handbook, that contains communication procedures for management bodies, the definition of communication flows, tools and methods, a contact list, operational procedures for meetings, information on collaborative spaces (project Intranet EMDESK) and teleconferences, confidentiality and intellectual property right issues.

1.5 Networking with other projects

CIRC-PACK partners will constantly work at expanding their network by reaching out to peers in the same or related sectors and engaging with the previously-mentioned stakeholder categories. Particular attention will be given to actors involved in other similar projects funded by the European Commission, especially within (but not limited to) the same call, in order to stimulate synergies and promote the use of existing solutions and tools (e.g. this [Waste Prevention Support Tool](#) created in the framework of another EU-funded project).

Candidate projects from the same call - related to CIRC-PACK topics - are:

- [PolyCE](#) - Post-Consumer High-tech Recycled Polymers for a Circular Economy
- [FiberEUse](#) - Large scale demonstration of new circular economy value-chains based on the reuse of end-of-life fiber reinforced composites
- [ECOBULK](#) - Circular Process for Eco-Designed Bulky Products and Internal Car Parts
- [PAPERCHAIN](#) - New market niches for the Pulp and Paper Industry waste based on circular economy approaches
- [PlastiCircle](#) - Improvement of the plastic packaging waste chain from a circular economy approach (further detailed below*)

Every CIRC-PACK partner commits to participate in at least two national or international events, forums or tradeshow promoting the project, its outcomes and benefits through the delivery of a PowerPoint, paper or poster presentations, workshops and/or communication materials at stands. ICLEI will provide partners with

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leaflets and project business cards to be used on these occasions for public relations and, together with Plastipolis, will seek participation in events at the EU level.

In order to foster and facilitate networking activities, a preliminary [calendar of over 120 upcoming international events of potential interest](#) - taking place in 2017, 2018 and 2019 - has been created and shared with partners through the Intranet.

This calendar will be regularly updated by CIRCE, ICLEI and all partners. The proposed events mainly focus on advanced materials and composites, polymer sourcing and biopolymers, plastics processing, green chemistry, innovative multilayer packaging design, sorting and control technologies, recycling, waste management, circular economy, public procurement, resource efficiency, sustainable cities, and investors in bio-based technologies. The list also includes events related to other EU-funded projects (e.g. a LIFE symposium on waste management and landfills and a LIFE platform meeting on plastic and the circular economy), as well as events related to a specific partner or industry involved in the project (e.g. plastics for the automobile, the cosmetic or the disposable food containers sector). Although we consider that the preferred geographical focus for communication and dissemination activities should be Europe, several intercontinental events have been added to promote lessons learnt and results at the global scale.

The same collaborative document has been shared also with the consortium of PlastiCircle, whose communication activities are also managed by ICLEI. This will help create and maintain synergies between the two projects, which will benefit from contributions from both sides. As previously mentioned, shared social media accounts have also been set up for CIRC-PACK and PlastiCircle to maximise the audience and crosslink activities.

[UrbanWINS](#), another H2020-funded project on waste reduction and management strategies whose communication is managed by ICLEI, will represent another preferential partner.

The following platforms have shown to be among the best sources where to identify future events in the sector and share CIRC-PACK events for a broad dissemination:

- [Circular Economy Club](#)
- [European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform](#)
- [The European Commission's selection of circular economy events](#)
- [AMI Plastics International conferences and exhibitions](#)
- [Sustainable Procurement Platform](#)
- [International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry](#)
- [Recycling International](#)
- [Conference Series](#)
- [Plastics Recyclers](#)
- [PETCore Europe](#) (especially for workshops)
- [Techtour](#)
- [Packaging World](#) (events and webinars)
- [Open Source Circular Economy Days](#)
- [Conference Locate](#)
- [10 times](#)

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Events organised by the EU also offer excellent opportunities for collaboration with staff, other stakeholders, potential new partners and investors. These include Horizon 2020 information days and brokerage events, the European Week of Regions and Cities, Green Week, and events promoted through the [EU Newsroom calendar](#). This list may be expanded integrated other relevant sources as this document is revised.

Additionally, linking with existing consortia and platforms will increase the visibility of CIRC-PACK and raise awareness on the messages it aims to convey. Such consortia and platforms include Zero Waste Europe, Zero Waste Municipality, Municipal Waste Europe, European Federation of Waste Management and Environmental Services, Sustainable Process Industry through Resource and Energy Efficiency, Extended Producer Responsibility Alliance, Plastics Europe, Extended Producer Responsibility Alliance. This interaction can take place both in person and online through the ICLEI-managed Public Procurement Forum, LinkedIn, or news and link exchange with other project websites (e.g. this [LIFE project on multi-layer packaging recycling](#)), through other partners and associations' channels or thematic portals (e.g. Europe's plastic processors).

1.6 Validation, monitoring, tracking, reporting and evaluation

All partners can create and publish content (for instance, news items, social media posts, leaflets, PowerPoint presentations, posters) in their own language whenever it is not possible to use the project tools developed by ICLEI in English, to better target national audiences and further amplify the messages in their countries.

PPT presentations and print products will need to be shared with ICLEI for validation two weeks before being used/published. ICLEI will check adherence to key messages (and may ask for a summary in English for this purpose), as well as the correct application of the templates. Partners will remain responsible for scientific content.

Two different monitoring tools (spreadsheets) have been created to track all communication and dissemination activities.

The first tool will be used by ICLEI to track the project website, newsletter and social media statistics, as well as press actions and impact (Google Alerts have been set up for this purpose), events organised within the framework of the project, print and audio-visual materials published.

The second one, shared with partners through the project Intranet EMDESK, will be used to monitor partners' activities including any communication content produced, the dissemination of press releases, the type and size of the audience reached, the participation in external events, networking activities with Horizon 2020 projects and the scientific publications issued. The categories taken into account to build these templates include but are not limited to the ones requested on the European Commission's reporting templates. Additional materials such as pictures taken at events, agendas, participants' lists and presentations will be also collected in a specific folder on the Intranet.

This information and materials will serve as a base for WP8 reporting activities scheduled for month 24 and month 36.

The following indicators will be used for evaluation:

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- **Web statistics** - number of unique visitors and downloads of documents;
- **Newsletter statistics** - number of subscribers, open rate and click-through rate;
- **Social media feedback** - number of followers and interaction (retweets, use of project hashtag, mentions, replays, impressions, shares, video visualisations);
- **Events** - number of workshops and other events organised, number of participants, international coverage;
- **Press impact** - number of releases published and contacts they were sent to, number of articles published on websites and media outlets.

Table 4. Communication and dissemination indicators for evaluation

Minimum targets to be achieved by the end of the project					
Website	Newsletter	Social media	Videos	Events	Media actions
2,000 unique visitors	200 subscribers	200 total followers for Twitter and LinkedIn	1,000 total views	20 participants in each workshop and 50 in the conference	5 press releases in total, and at least 20 press mentions per year

Deliverable submission, quality control and reporting procedures, as well as intellectual property rights issues are described in the Consortium Agreement and in Deliverable 1.1. - Project Handbook.

1.7 Dissemination activities after the project ends

Communication and dissemination activities will continue after the end of the project to ensure the exploitation of results.

In particular, the project website will be maintained online for two more years, and ICLEI will continue managing the social media accounts and the Forum created on circular economy, integrating information from new projects and enlarging the audience.

All partners will continue their engagement by communicating and disseminating CIRC-PACK messages, findings and benefits at events even after month 36 in order to ensure maximum replication, and using the lessons learnt as well as the network of contacts acquired for future projects and scientific publications.

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2 PLAN

Which channels and products for which stakeholder groups?

Table 5. Channels and products for each target group

	Project website + newsletter	Social media and Forum	Leaflets	Posters	Breakfast at Sustainability, workshops, conference	Press releases and press kit	Videos	Partners' online channels and magazines	Participation in external events
Public authorities and regulators	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X
Value chain actors	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X
Waste / recycling companies	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X
Scientific community	X		X	X	X			X	X
Consumers	X	X	X				X	X	
Potential investors	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X
Media	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X
Other multipliers	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	

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Timeline and work plan

Table 6. Summary of activities, responsibilities and deadlines

Year	2017									2018									2019									2020								
Month	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36
T.8.1. Strategically planned dissemination (Responsible: ICLEI)																																				
<i>Comm. and dissemination plan, (and x2 revision)</i>						6						12												24												
<i>Review of comm. and dissemination activities</i>																								24												36
<i>Newsletter</i>								9			12		15		18		21			24		27					30		33						36	
<i>Social media (x3 weekly)</i>								9																												36
<i>Website updates (ongoing)</i>						6																														36
<i>Final report on comm. and dissemination activities</i>																																				36
T8.2 Creation of dissemination materials (Responsible: ICLEI)																																				
<i>Logo & visual identity</i>	1					6																														
<i>Setup of social media channels</i>				4																																
<i>Word Agenda template</i>				4																																
<i>Header and footer (for brochures, etc.)</i>				4																																
<i>Word Minutes Template</i>					5																															
<i>Word Deliverable template</i>					5																															
<i>Website design/development</i>						6						12																								
<i>PowerPoint presentation template</i>						6																														
<i>Written identity</i>						6																														
<i>Videos (x2, CIRCE and ICLEI responsible)</i>								8																										32		
<i>Infographic</i>												12																								
<i>Brochure (aka "leaflet")</i>												12																								
<i>Posters (x2)</i>												12																						32		
<i>Roll up banner</i>												12																								

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3 CONCLUSIONS

The Communication and Dissemination Plan plays a key role in the success of the project, as it provides consortium partners with guidance as well as useful resources and tools to be used to:

- Establish a recognisable brand of CIRC-PACK;
- Be present and visible at the main events in the sector in the international arena, to get updates which may be relevant to consider for the project, increase their network and spread project results;
- To create awareness and influence stakeholders to maximise exploitation and replication;
- To make the most of the opportunity to participate in a European project as well as of the grant received.

Stakeholder engagement should not be seen as an accessory activity to be carried out at the end of the project, but as one of the main, ongoing pillars of CIRC-PACK, running in parallel to the Demo cases. Stakeholders' interest will need to be stimulated and grow together with the development of the project in order to convince them of the viability of CIRC-PACK solutions, ultimately leading to adoption of the solutions being developed.

It is therefore of utmost importance that all partners understand the high stakes and contribute - at their requested level - to communication and dissemination activities within their country and beyond, whenever possible, under the guidance of WP8 leader.

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4 ANNEXES

5.1 ANNEX A: H2020 emblem, legal content and disclaimer

The EU emblem. Normal reproduction in colour recommended.

In accordance with the Commission's guidelines on visual identity, all H2020 EU programmes must be identified exclusively by the EU emblem (neither the European Commission nor the programme logos) and the mention of the programme name. Projects must display the EU emblem (which is available to download in different qualities and sizes from: <http://europa.eu/about-eu/basic-information/symbols/flag>) on infrastructure, equipment, results (see instructions on D.1.1) as well as on communication and dissemination products and channels. The basic rules summarized below make particular reference to the latter.

The minimum height of the EU emblem shall be 1 cm. The name of the European Union shall always be spelled out in full. The typeface to be used in conjunction with the EU emblem can be any of the following: Arial, Calibri, Garamond, Trebuchet, Tahoma, Verdana. Italic and underlined variations are not allowed. The positioning of the text in relation to the EU emblem is not prescribed in any particular way but the text should not interfere with the emblem in any way. The font size used should be proportionate to the size of the emblem. The colour of the font should be reflex blue (same blue colour of the EU flag), black or white depending on the background.

For more information:

http://ec.europa.eu/dgs/communication/services/visual_identity/pdf/use-emblem_en.pdf

The following text needs to be added:

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Disclaimer: The sole responsibility for any error or omissions lies with the editor. The content does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The European Commission is also not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

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	Reference:	D8.1	Date:	31/10/17

5.2 ANNEX B: Screenshots of website design and press kit

The CIRC-PACK website is live at: www.circpack.eu

Some screenshots can be found below, although the live website may appear different due to continuous updates.

The CIRC-PACK landing page (homepage)

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Demo case A: Plastics from renewable resources

The first demonstration will focus on producing biodegradable or compostable polyesters with enhanced properties using renewable resources instead of fossil feedstock. These new plastics will be used for the manufacturing of trays, bottles, coffee capsules, jars, films and pallets. They are also expected to improve the recycling rates of the automotive and hygiene product industries, and increase the amount of recycled materials in products such as car parts, sanitary towels and nappies.

Downloads
No downloads are available yet.

Contact
Lead organisation: **BUMADA**

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Page for Demo cast A: Plastic from renewable resources

Demo case B: Eco-friendly packaging designs

The second demonstration will improve the recyclability of multilayer and multi-material packaging (including, for instance, paper or different types of plastics), which is known for being difficult to recycle. This will be achieved through smart eco-designs - which will use the new materials developed during the first demonstration - that make it easier to collect, sort and recycle the waste, reducing environmental impact.

Downloads
No downloads are available yet.

Contact
Lead organisation: **Novamont**

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Page for Demo case B: Eco-friendly packaging designs

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	Author:	ICLEI EURO	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D8.1	Date:	31/10/17

Page for Demo case C: Enhanced sorting and recycling

Project media page

	Document:	D8.1. Communication and Dissemination plan (CDP)		
	Author:	ICLEI EURO	Version:	1.0
	Reference:	D8.1	Date:	31/10/17

CIRC-PACK – Project factsheet

Acronym and title
The acronym of the project must be used always in capital letters, with the hyphen. The use of the full title is optional.
CIRC-PACK – Towards circular economy in the plastic packaging value chain

Tagline (Claim)
A new circular economy for the plastic packaging sector value chain.

One sentence
The CIRC-PACK project will develop alternative bio-based and recyclable plastics, and new types of multilayer and multi-material packaging, while sorting and recycling processes will be enhanced, promoting the circular economy and leading to a more sustainable future.

Bullet points
The CIRC-PACK project will focus on:

- Seeking and validating 100% new biodegradable materials from renewable resources for applications along the plastic value chain;
- The design and validation of new packaging solutions that will enable and/or facilitate the end-of-life separation of materials;
- The use of recycled materials as raw materials and the creation of closed-loop recycling flows, as well as of a multi-sector cascade recycling process;
- Addressing the legal restrictions, bottlenecks and other non-technological barriers to facilitate a broader transition to the circular economy;
- Developing a life-cycle methodology to assess the performance of the new value chain in terms of circularity improvement;
- The demonstration of the environmental, social and economic impact and sustainability of the new circular value chain contributing to the uptake of project solutions;
- The development of new sustainable business models to enable a circular use of plastic materials.

Half page
CIRC-PACK (Towards circular economy in the plastic packaging value chain) is a three-year EU-funded project that aims to develop a more sustainable, efficient, **competitive**, less fossil fuel dependent, integrated and interconnected plastic value chain.

To this end, the consortium will work in the following three areas with three demo cases:

- decoupling the chain from fossil feedstock;
- introducing innovative formats and reducing the negative environmental impact of plastic packaging; and
- creating** an effective after-use plastics economy.

The CIRC-PACK project will provide breakthrough biodegradable plastics using alternative bio-based raw materials, which will have an instrumental role to play along the plastic value chain. In addition, smart eco-design measures will be developed and adapted also to the new bio-based materials previously developed, to facilitate the collection and recycling of multilayer and multi-material packaging. These innovations will contribute to greatly reduce the packaging footprint, by increasing the bio-based content and using compostable materials.

CIRC-PACK, Towards circular economy in the plastic packaging value chain 1

CIRC-PACK – Project factsheet

Finally, a multi-sectorial approach along the plastic packaging value chain will be applied, which will have critical impacts also in other value chains (automotive and absorbents), increasing the typology of materials, valuable sub-products and the amount of recycled materials used.

All CIRC-PACK activities will be supported by non-technological and advanced methodological analysis in order to facilitate the transition from the current linear plastic packaging value chain to circular economy principles, which will trigger a broad deployment of the tested solutions.

In addition, awareness raising activities targeting consumers and related stakeholders will boost an enabling regulatory environment, the replicability of developed solutions and the adoption of new business models.

The CIRC-PACK project is in line with the objectives of the platform representing **Plastics Recyclers Europe** and the PPP Bio-based Industries, as well as with European Commission's challenges regarding a better management of waste, expecting an increase of the collecting rate up to 48% and a reduction of landfilling rate up to 15% by 2020.

Key messages by technologies

Technology
CIRC-PACK demonstrates and validates, bridging the innovation gap, several technological innovations. Indeed, some of the systems to be piloted in CIRC-PACK, such as the polymerization process, are new technologies that, once demonstrated by the project, will open up a pathway to their commercialisation. This brings a new opportunity for the technology manufacture plastic industry to develop around the outputs of CIRC-PACK. CIRC-PACK will strengthen the competitiveness of the European plastic sector through the recyclability, the cost reduction related to extracting and transporting raw material resources and the high quality which has always been a relevant referent of the European plastics. Through this project, the European plastic sector will be boosted: this sector aims to grow at the same rate than the global plastic production, around 14% annually.

Economy
CIRC-PACK proposes - through the circular economy - a cost reduction related to extracting and transporting raw material resources, which will boost the European plastic industry to lead the high global competitiveness. The CIRC-PACK results penetration in the market could rise the turnover of the European plastic sector up to 5 Bio € / year by 2030. This result will support the target from the European Commission to increase the industrial share of Europe's GDP from 15.3% to 20% by 2020. Furthermore, the plastic sector has a multiplier effect throughout the other plastic-user value chains (healthcare, energy generation, aerospace, automotive, maritime, construction, electronics, textile, etc.) therefore an increase of 10% in the value added of the European plastics sector could lead to a 4.4% increase in the value added of the whole EU manufacturing sector.

Environment
CIRC-PACK will contribute to the zero plastics to landfill by 2025 by a faster reduction of the quantity of plastics to landfill. The deployment of measures as CIRC-PACK will achieve to avoid 60 million tonnes of plastics during the period 2025-2037, equivalent to over 750 million barrels of oil or 60 billion euros.

CIRC-PACK, Towards circular economy in the plastic packaging value chain 2

The written identity of the project (Project Factsheet), part of the press kit